

DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN TOWARDS NEW REFORMS

Tilaev Ermat Rahmatovich

Shahrisabz State Pedagogical Institute, Dean of the Faculty of Social Sciences, Candidate of technical sciences

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10599741>

Abstract. *This article will explore the development of tourism in Uzbekistan along with new reformations in different spheres of the life. Tourism and its development preparation will be supported by real construction and reformations samples being taken all around the touristic zones.*

Keywords: *tourism service, reformation, revenue, museums, laws.*

After the independence of Uzbekistan, reforms were carried out in all spheres of economic, social, spiritual and cultural life, including, under the leadership of our honorable President, special attention was paid to the tourism sector as well as to the improvement of holy places. Great attention has been paid to the restoration of our national tradition and national values, to the deep study of our rich heritage, and to wide promotion of its essence and importance among our people, especially among the youth. Great attention has been paid to the restoration of our national tradition and values, to the deep study of our rich heritage, and to wide promotion of its essence and importance among our people, especially among the youth. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Museums" and the Decree of of the First President Islam Karimov on January 12, 1998 "On the Fundamental Improvement and Improvement of the Activities of Museums" served as an important basis for organizing the work of museums and strengthening their material and technical base. Was made Resolution of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 177 on the Law on Museums on September 12, 2008, Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 68 "Approving the Regulatory Legal Documents Necessary for the Implementation of the Law on Museums" on April 12, 2010 of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6000 dated May 26, 2020 on "Measures to further increase the role and influence of the sphere of culture and art in the life of society" serves these reforms are for the benefit of the people. President Shavkat Mirziyoev paid great attention not only to the field of museums, but also to the field of tourism. On the initiative of our head of state, a study program on Pilgrimage tourism will be developed.

In the speech of the President on Tourism - the driver of the economy of Uzbekistan, he suggested that "there are more than 8,200 objects of cultural heritage in our country, and 500 of them are included in the tourism route. We need to take measures to increase the number of objects on the routes, where it is possible to develop pilgrimage and traditional tourism, to 800"¹ passed.

Starting from the 2021-2022 academic year, a study program on pilgrimage tourism was developed and implemented for 3-4 year students of higher education institutions training foreign language specialists. It was announced in this form in the decision Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 100 of the on "Additional measures for the development of domestic and pilgrimage tourism - activities".

During the period 2010-2017, the volume of export of tourism services doubled and amounted to 546.9 million US dollars in 2017 and 1041 million US dollars in 2018. Until 2016,

the growth rate of the number of foreign visitors was 8 percent on average, and in 2017 - 7 percent, exceeding 2.69 million people. By the end of 2018, 5.3 million foreign tourists visited the republic. As a result of taking measures to support and protect the private sector, the number of tourism organizations, which was 398 in 2015, increased to 950 by the end of 2018, and the number of hotel establishments increased from 661 to 900.

A number of decisions, decrees and orders are issued on tourism and domestic tourism. In his speeches, our president emphasized the role of domestic tourism in the development of the country's economy, and emphasized that our people should go to some small vacation spots in our country with their family members. At the same time, the seminars on "Museum Management" held in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and Tashkent by young scientists in cooperation with the "Uzbek Museum" Foundation and the National Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan for UNESCO are a clear example of this. They were attended by a group of experts consisting of representatives of the State Museum of the History of Uzbekistan, the State Art Museum of Uzbekistan, the State Museum of the History of the Timurids, the Geological Museum of Uzbekistan, the International Amir Temur Foundation, and the National Institute of Painting and Design named after Kamoliddin Behzod. If we take schoolchildren, students of vocational schools, and young students to these museums and show them our history, their love for the motherland will increase even more.

The youth of our country paid special attention to young people, "Issues of establishing museums in Uzbekistan", "Procedure of accounting for museum objects and museum collections", "Scientific concept of the museum", "Services for visitors and issues of cooperation in museum activities", "Pedagogical involvement of children in museums" The lectures on topics such as "the role of technologies" and "Prospects of the Virtual Museum" undoubtedly had a special place in enriching the knowledge of the participants of the event.

In fact, during the years of independence, the scope of noble efforts and efforts aimed at the development of tourism, domestic tourism, and museums is incomparable. Due to the high attention, many more museums were built, and the work of the existing ones was started at the level of the requirements of the time, and museum-reserves were established. Our opinion is confirmed by the construction of dozens of museums, such as the State Museum of the History of the Timurids, the State Museum of the History of Uzbekistan, the Museum of Remembrance of the Victims of Catagon, the Archaeological Museum of Termiz, the Museum of Olympic Glory, and the renovation of open-air museums in the cities of Samarkand, Bukhara, and Khiva. All these achievements, the tourists who visited our capital, the reforms carried out in our country serve for the benefit of the people. Tourists visiting our capital can mention several cities with developed tourism such as Samarkand, Khiva, Bukhara, Ko'kan, Shahrisabz, the prestigious cities of Uzbekistan. It should be said that in the development of domestic tourism, all regional governors are paying attention to beautification works in the tourist places in their territory. In addition to domestic tourism, museology is a wide field of science that includes history, archeology, art studies, and the field of museology operates at the National Institute of Painting and Design named after Kamoliddin Behzod. This educational institution is the only place of learning that prepares personnel for the field. Here, students study at bachelor's, master's and doctoral levels. In this regard, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated July 11, 2014 "On measures to ensure the openness of state museums to children and their parents" educates the growing young generation in the spirit of love for the Motherland, loyalty to the ideas of independence, respect for national

and universal values, they it should be emphasized that it was another important step in instilling in the minds of the rich national cultural heritage and historical past of our people respect and admiration and meaningful organization of recreation of the population. According to this decision, every Tuesday and Friday of the week, children under the age of 18 and their accompanying parents are admitted to state museums free of charge. On this day, Uzbek museums introduce the public to new aspects of their activities, open days are held, and various exhibitions are organized². In short, domestic tourism and travel to museums have a special place in educating a spiritually mature, perfect person. Historical monuments, historical monuments, rare manuscripts and documents preserved in our country tell the history, life and high spirituality of our ancestors. This instills in the hearts of young people a feeling of respect, honor and love for the heritage left by our ancestors, and also forms in them the feeling of being a dear and worthy child.

REFERENCES

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг Фармони. “Ўзбекистон Республикасида ички туризмни янада ривожлантириш чора – тадбирлари тўғрисида” Халқ сўзи. 2021 йил 10 феврал. № 29
2. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Шавкат Мирзиёевнинг Олий Мажлисга Мурожаатномасини ўрганиш ва кенг жамоатчилик ўртасида тарғиб этишга бағишланган илмий – оммабоп қўлланма. – Т.: Маънавият, 2019. – Б. 190
3. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Шавкат Мирзиёев раислигидаги 2018 – йил 22 – феврал куни ведиоселектор йиғилишидаги нутқлари.
4. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Вазирлар Маҳкамасининг 30. 05.2019 йилдаги 443-сонли қарори.
5. Туризм соҳасини юксалтиришда илмий ёндашув зарур. Халқ сўзи. 2020 йил 25 декабр. № 272.
6. “Туризм тўғрисидаги” Ўзбекистон Республикаси Қонуни. Ўзбекистоннинг янги қонунлари. Тошкент., 2019-йил 18-июл, ЎРҚ-549-сон.